

**Arctic
Research
Consortium
of the
United States**

Member Institutions:

University of Alaska
Anchorage
University of Alaska
Fairbanks
University of Alaska
Statewide
Alaska North Slope Borough
Dept. of Wildlife Management
Arizona State University
Bates College
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12 May 2003

Simon Stephenson
Arctic Research Support and Logistics Program Manager
Office of Polar Programs, Room 755
National Science Foundation
4201 Wilson Blvd.
Arlington, VA 22230

Dear Mr. Stephenson:

Enclosed is one copy of the 2nd Annual Report of the Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) as required in Section F-1 of Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279, between the National Science Foundation and ARCUS. The report describes accomplishments for the period 1 April 2002 through 31 March 2003 and outlines projected activities for the period 1 April 2003 through 31 March 2004.

Included in the annual report, as specified in the Cooperative Agreement, are:

- An executive summary outlining the major activities and accomplishments during the period of this cooperative agreement;
- a narrative summary of accomplishments, future plans, and discussion of major change in direction or pace, by individual task;
- a one-page summary showing costs by five major tasks; arctic community science planning, NSF Arctic Sciences Section coordination, arctic science education, information and outreach, and core support (Attachment A).
- a five-page, multi-column table, by individual activity, showing the currently approved five-year budget, the approved budget for year one, actual expenditures through January 2003, projected expenditures February and March 2003, the remaining funds or shortfall expected, and the proposed budget for April 2003-March 2004 (Attachment B);
- a one-page, multi-column table summarizing the entire cooperative agreement by Form 1030 categories and showing the currently approved budget, actual expenditures through January 2003, projected expenditures for February and March 2003, the remaining funds or shortfall expected, and the proposed budget for April 2003-March 2004 (Attachment C); and
- the proposed budget for April 2003-March 2004 on NSF Form 1030 (Attachment D).

The ARCUS board of directors and staff are pleased at the achievements of the past year and the work accomplished on behalf of the arctic research community and NSF. We look forward to continuing to work with NSF and the arctic research community on these important initiatives. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me.

Sincerely,

Wendy K. Warnick
Executive Director

Enclosures

cc: ARCUS Board of Directors

THE ARCTIC RESEARCH CONSORTIUM OF THE UNITED STATES

Annual Report Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279 April 2002 through March 2003

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) has undertaken a variety of activities to enhance NSF arctic research programs, through Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279. ARCUS has worked with the scientific community to identify new research objectives, logistical requirements, and educational activities that benefit planning and implementation of NSF-supported science initiatives in the Arctic. Specific activities have been organized under four major tasks:

1. Arctic science planning—coordinating science planning for the arctic research community at several levels, including continuing examination of logistical requirements with the goal of improved access for all researchers in the Arctic;
2. Organizational support for research programs included in the Office of Polar Programs Arctic Sciences Section—the Arctic System Science Program, the Arctic Social Sciences Program, and the Arctic Natural Sciences Program;
3. Development and coordination of arctic science educational activities; and
4. Information and outreach activities disseminating timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, and to the public.

An additional 5th “task” is the provision of core support for ARCUS’ NSF-funded activities—dedicated funding of the infrastructure necessary to support this work regardless of the specific nature of activities from year-to-year.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

Accomplishments under this major task include activities to address arctic research support and logistics needs, including:

- Updating the arctic logistics recommendations to provide long-term advice on arctic logistics and science support issues for the NSF Office of Polar Programs;
- Continuing development and maintenance of ALIAS, an arctic research support and logistics web site that serves as an information resource and access point for the research community; and
- Planning and coordinating a large international Open Science Meeting for the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) program.
- Convening a working group and supporting a workshop to prepare recommendations to NSF for a research program on the Bering Sea, called Bering Ecological Study (BEST).
- Reprinting and distributing the brochure for *SEARCH: The Study of Environmental Arctic Change*, for the SEARCH Interagency Working Group and the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

Accomplishments under this major task include several activities for the ARCSS Program and the Arctic Social Sciences Program, as well as the development of informational posters on aspects of arctic research for the Arctic Section as a whole.

2.2 ARCTIC SYSTEM SCIENCE (ARCSS) PROGRAM COORDINATION

Activities under this sub-task include:

- Providing organizational support to the work of the ARCSS Committee (AC) and the AC chair.

- Coordinating discussions and planning for adjustments in the structure and process for ARCSS Program community science management.
- Coordinating the preparations for an ARCSS-wide synthesis effort.
- Developing and coordinating the work of an ARCSS program data committee.
- Publishing the proceedings of the 2002 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop.

2.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

Accomplishments under this sub-task include:

- Preliminary planning for an arctic social sciences community-wide conference, *Partnering with Arctic Communities*, which will be convened in Fall 2003.
- Preparation of an updated second edition of *Arctic Social Sciences: Opportunities in Arctic Research* for publication in 2003.
- Publication and distribution of *The Earth is Faster Now*, a compilation of research on indigenous observations of Arctic environmental change.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

Activities under this major task include:

- Coordinating and participating in a community-based collaborative science education project *Eider Journey*, which provides research experiences for arctic students and teachers.
- Collaborating with Arctic Native organizations and arctic researchers to develop indigenous curriculum materials and to return research results to northern communities, and
- Managing an Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community.
- Planning for and developing curriculum materials for *The 2003 Ecological Change Expedition*, a virtual field trip developed as part of the distance delivery education program Arctic Alive! and scheduled to begin in April 2003. The *2003 Ecological Change Expedition* will focus on ecological research in Kotzebue Sound, Alaska and will include information on using traditional knowledge as well as western scientific research practices.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

Accomplishments related to information distribution and outreach include:

- Publishing and distributing two issues of *Witness the Arctic* to over 8,500 subscribers.
- Developing and maintaining web-based resources for arctic research.
- Managing the Arctic Info listserv.
- Maintaining and expanding *The Directory of Arctic Researchers*.
- Developing the online archive infrastructure, metadata structure, submission guidelines, and legal use contracts for the Internet Graphics Archive.
- Convening the two-day *Arctic Forum*, a seminar highlighting important arctic research findings, in Arlington, VA in May 2002, as well as publishing the abstract volume from the seminar.

5. CORE SUPPORT

Accomplishments described in Core Support are direct project activities that benefit and support multiple NSF activities that cannot be identified with one specific project.

THE ARCTIC RESEARCH CONSORTIUM OF THE UNITED STATES

2nd Annual Report

April 2002–March 2003

OPP-0101279

The narrative describes activity for the period April 2002 through March 2003, the second year of Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279. Accomplishments and work in progress are described through March 2003, and projected activities are indicated for the period April 2003 through March 2004.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.1 Arctic Research Support and Logistics

Accomplishments

- The ten-member Research Support and Logistics Working Group (RSLWG) met four times by teleconference in the past year, and held one working group meeting, in conjunction with the September 2002 AAAS Arctic Science Conference in Fairbanks, Alaska. The teleconference and in-person discussions were held to develop information and additional material for key gaps in the report's content identified during a series of reviews by working group members and other invited reviewers.
- Working group members continued to work on writing assignments and worked with selected researchers to develop draft materials for the remaining gaps identified in the updated report.
- RSLWG co-chairs Terry Tucker and Peter Schlosser met with ARCUS staff 11 times throughout the year, in person and by teleconference, to discuss progress and identify outstanding contributions needed or requested.
- The draft report was prepared in layout with figures, maps and photographs and distributed for working group and invited review in March 2003.

Projected Activities

- Distribute the penultimate draft report, in layout and with completed figures, maps, and photos, for broad community review in May 2003.
- Revise the draft report in June 2003, based on comments received during month-long community review.
- Publish and distribute final report in July 2003.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Working group co-chairs Schlosser and Tucker revised the timeline for completion of the report to July 2003. Delays in production were necessary in part to develop critical sections and recommendations further and to receive contributions from members of the arctic research community. The goals and scope of the activities are unchanged, however.

1.2 Logistics Internet Resources; Arctic Logistics Information and Support (ALIAS)

Accomplishments

- Developed a prioritized list of countries, resources, and field sites and a "mailing list" of resource managers and other information sources to gather information for the site.
- Solicited resource manager and user participation in submitting logistics information via the electronic survey process.
- Researched and developed database sections for 24 field sites, which are now dynamically displayed on ALIAS. Field site information includes site manager

contact information, logistics support providers, permitting requirements, access issues, information about available resources at the site, and links to other resources, as well as many other important informational categories.

- Researched and developed database sections for 19 vessels, which are now dynamically displayed on ALIAS. Vessel information includes ownership and management, physical characteristics (including performance capability), onboard scientific equipment and space, communications and data equipment available, as well as many other important informational categories.
- Developed a secondary or “meta” database to manage the metadata essential to operating the main database. This secondary database facilitates data management functions by allowing the staff to manage contact information, create mailing lists as needed, monitor data currency, coordinate with other staff, provide documentation for project continuity, and capture and organize information for input and other purposes.
- Designed and implemented a system for making all hyperlinks on the ALIAS web site database-rendered, to enable efficient single-point updating of links site wide, avoiding the dead links common on large web sites.
- As it is developed, ALIAS will help researchers to assess the feasibility of working in a specific area, identify research platforms from which research could be accomplished, plan the conduct of research, view current research in a given area, including maps and publications, and make scientific and logistics support contacts.

Projected Activities

- Expand the above process into all planned coverage areas: Types of Platforms (Vessels, etc.), Data Resources, and Map resources.
- Develop an interactive cruise track database and interface for arctic research cruises, that links to information about vessels with varied levels of capability, and to investigator and project information.
- Coordinate and plan with VECO Polar Resources, other logistics providers, and site managers to provide seamless access to information about field sites, funded projects, and publications based on work accomplished in various regions and at field sites.
- Develop comparative web-available search interface for the entire ALIAS database.
- Develop online interface for submission of logistics information by managers and users that submits directly to the database and eliminates manual data entry process.
- Address additional goals including:
 - Web site accessibility (ADA compliant version);
 - Additional web-based support for the research community, such as providing an online meeting space, information about funding opportunities, logistics bulletin boards for transportation and equipment sharing, research "classifieds", online request-response forum for information.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

During the past year work on the ALIAS project has focused on continued development of the ALIAS database, so that all information contained on the site is available as a dynamic resource. With the structure in place to dynamically receive and display logistics data from multiple sources around the world, ALIAS will have the capability to update in near-real time on a global scale. Several minor changes in the direction of short-term development have been initiated by requests from the NSF Arctic Section head for additional resources or specific information to be made available but there have been no major changes in long-term pace or direction.

1.3 Planning for Integrated Arctic Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

Accomplishments

- This project was deemed completed by agreement with the NSF Arctic Research Support and Logistics Program Manager in April 2002. Ongoing activities included printing hard copies and distributing them upon request, of the Phase I report, titled *Recommendations for a Geographic Information Infrastructure to Support Arctic Research: Outcomes of the Arctic GIS Workshop*, published online in April 2001.

Projected Activities

- No further activities are planned at this time.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

The project has been completed.

1.4 SEARCH Planning; Convening the First SEARCH Open Science Meeting

ARCUS will coordinate and convene the first open science meeting for the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH). The meeting will be held 27–30 October 2003 in Seattle, Washington. The primary goal of the Open Science Meeting (OSM) is to inform a broad research community about research that addresses the basic premise of SEARCH, that there exists a complex of interrelated pan-Arctic changes occurring across terrestrial, oceanic, atmospheric and human systems. It is anticipated that these results will inspire scientists from a large range of disciplines to contribute to SEARCH either through linking their ongoing work to this program or through the design of new projects. Understanding the interdependence of these changes and their relation to mid-latitudes represents a major research challenge, both in the international and U.S. arenas. The Open Science Meeting will be a forum for presentation and discussion of recent scientific findings that document these large changes, as well as the exchange of new ideas that will contribute to solving the questions posed by the observations.

Accomplishments

- Worked with the NSF program manager and the SEARCH science steering committee chair to select and appoint meeting organizing committee members and to select a chair for the organizing committee process.
- Selected the workshop venue and began making arrangements for the necessary technical and logistic support. Identified nearby hotels and began making arrangements for accommodations for meeting participants.
- Assisted the organizing committee to develop the priorities for the meeting and to determine the structure and focus of the sessions to be held during the meeting.
- Prepared First and Second announcements about the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, which were distributed to the community via Arctic Info, as well as during Arctic Science Summit week, and other relevant U.S. and international meetings.
- Developed an online pre-registration process to encourage interested participants to pre-register for the meeting.
- Began development of an online abstract submission process that would allow users or the organizing committee members to select a category for the submission and to identify whether a poster abstract or presentation abstract is being submitted.

Projected Activities

- Prepare and post background material and full registration information for the meeting on the ARCUS web site. Complete the online abstract submission process and database so that all submitted abstracts can be viewed online in the appropriate categories.

- Distribute a Third Announcement, a broad community invitation to the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, including a call for abstracts, via Arctic Info, other electronic lists, and the ARCUS web site.
- Work with the organizing committee to develop a process for assessing and determining merit-based travel support for potential participants in need of additional support.
- Complete the roster of invited keynote speakers, prepare instructions to speakers, and begin issuing invitations, with assistance from the organizing committee and the SEARCH science steering committee.
- Refine the topics for parallel science sessions at the meeting and recruit facilitators for the groups. Solicit short papers for presentation during the parallel science sessions.
- Circulate a call for organizations or groups wishing to host a side meeting before, during, or after the SEARCH Open Science Meeting and work with interested parties to coordinate the logistics and planning.
- Solicit media interest and prepare information for an organized media campaign related to SEARCH research priorities and relevant research findings.
- Post final agenda, participant list, and other meeting information on the ARCUS web site and distribute it to all registered participants via email in advance of the meeting.
- Coordinate travel and participant arrangements for the meeting. Pay travel for invited speakers, Organizing Committee members, and other participants receiving travel support, and pay for other meeting and support costs associated with the workshop.
- Prepare a compilation of the abstracts submitted prior to the workshop for distribution and review at the workshop. Publish proceedings, including abstracts, following the meeting.
- Provide staff support for the three or four-day, 300-participant workshop.
- Post follow-up information on the ARCUS web site after the workshop, including PDF and Powerpoint downloads of all the presentations and poster and presentation abstracts.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

1.5 Planning for Bering Sea Research: Bering Ecological Studies (BEST)

The NSF Arctic Sciences Section is supporting a planning process to initiate collaborative studies of the sub-arctic seas, culminating in cooperative ecological research of the eastern, western and basin areas by Japan, Russia and the United States. The planning process began with the *Ecosystem Studies of the Sub-arctic Seas* workshop in Laguna Beach California, 4-6 September 2002, after which a nineteen-member working group was formed to begin development of a draft science plan. ARCUS was tasked to coordinate the March 2003 meeting of the working group, to provide staff support for the development of the science plan, and to publish and distribute the plan when completed.

Accomplishments

- Worked with the BEST chair, organizing committee members, and the NSF program manager to select working group participants and advisors and observers to participate in the workshop discussions and planning process.
- Assisted the BEST working group chair to prepare the workshop agenda, and to compile and distribute relevant publications prior to the workshop.
- Prepared and posted background material and workshop information on the ARCUS web site.

- Prepared and distributed via Arctic Info a call for broad community contributions to the planning process. Compiled the information submitted for use in preparing the draft science plan.
- Posted the final agenda, participant list, working group instructions, and other meeting information on the ARCUS web site and distributed it to all registered participants via email in advance of the meeting.
- Coordinated all arrangements for the workshop venue and the necessary technical and logistic support. Coordinated travel and participant arrangements for the workshop.
- Provided staff support for the three-day, 23-participant workshop.
- Posted follow-up information on the ARCUS web site after the workshop, including PDF and Powerpoint downloads of all the presentations, the tentative timeline, writing assignments, and draft contributions.

Projected Activities

- Coordinate with working group members to complete writing assignments.
- Prepare first draft of the science plan and distribute for review.
- Plan and convene BEST session during the SEARCH open science meeting.
- Distribute revised draft science plan for community review.
- Hold BEST town meetings at AGU Fall meeting in December 2003, AGU Ocean Sciences meeting in January 2004, the ASLO/TOS meeting in February 2004, and the 2004 AAAS meeting.
- Publish and distribute science plan in Spring 2004.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

1.6 Workshop, to be determined

Accomplishments

- No activities in the past year.

Projected Activities

- No activities are planned in the coming year

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

1.7 Revision and Reprinting of the SEARCH Brochure

Accomplishments

- There were no activities in this project during the past year.

Projected Activities

- No further activities are planned in the near-term, although we receive many requests for the brochure and copies are no longer available. An updated publication may be considered as an outcome of the SEARCH Open Science Meeting.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS

Accomplishments

- Developed five interrelated posters on topics related to Arctic research for use by the NSF Arctic Section staff at scientific conferences and meetings. Themes from several of the posters were selected and combined for further development in the near-term.
- Developed and produced laminated copies of a general information poster about arctic research supported by the NSF Arctic Sciences Section for use in the NSF Office of Polar Programs (OPP) informational display. The poster was first displayed at the AGU meeting in San Francisco in December 2002.
- A jumbo PDF was provided to facilitate future printing.
- Began the initial development of a poster on arctic science education activities sponsored by the NSF Arctic Sciences Section, for inclusion in the NSF OPP informational display.

Projected Activities

- Complete the arctic science education poster.
- Provide laminated copies and a jumbo PDF to facilitate future printing.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Rather than producing five inter-related posters as originally requested, NSF Arctic Section staff suggested combining themes from several of the draft posters and producing one, which would fit more easily into the NSF OPP display.

2.2 ARCTIC SYSTEM SCIENCE (ARCSS) PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination

Accomplishments

- Reviewed the composition of the ARCSS Committee, with the AC chair and the NSF Program Director, in the context of new priorities and the representations of key programs and disciplinary perspectives and expertise.
- Selected and appointed new members to replace members due to rotate off the committee.
- Worked with ARCSS Committee chair to prepare materials for several meetings of the ten-member ARCSS Committee (AC) and ARCSS Program science steering committee chairs, and science management office directors to assess the direction of the ARCSS Program, research priorities, new planning underway, the current funding picture, and important opportunities.
- Provided the committee chair with a stipend and travel funds to participate in ARCSS-related meetings and workshops.
- Convened a teleconference meeting of the ARCSS Committee, science steering committee chairs, science management office directors, and the NSF ARCSS Program Director in August 2002 to review the recommendations from the All-Hands Workshop, as well as from various ongoing planning efforts, and to discuss plans for the Committee's work over the next several years.
- Convened a meeting of the ARCSS Committee in February 2003 to discuss new directions, planning within each component, program structure, and preparations for the March 2003 meeting of the ARCSS Committee and ARCSS Program leadership.

- Convened meetings of the ARCSS Committee and selected members of the ARCSS Program leadership in October 2002 and March 2003 to identify research priorities, recommend new ARCSS Program structure, and to prepare for short and long-term synthesis efforts to synthesize the first twelve years of ARCSS research.
- Assisted the ARCSS Committee chair with the development of materials, synthesis presentations, and communication processes to help ARCSS investigators identify important research findings, gaps in current understanding, and priorities for new ARCSS Program research.
- Began planning for a weeklong ARCSS Program synthesis retreat, scheduled for August 2003.
- Provided support for the development of an ARCSS Program data committee and initiated planning for the first committee meeting, scheduled for May 2003.
- Provided general support for ARCSS science steering committees, science management offices, and lead researchers working on new initiatives, preparing and distributing information, graphics, and publications about ARCSS Program research upon request.

Projected Activities

- Convene an ARCSS data committee meeting in Boulder, Colorado in May 2003.
- Convene the ARCSS Program synthesis retreat at Big Sky, Montana in August 2003.
- Convene a meeting of the ARCSS Committee in early Fall 2003, possibly in conjunction with the SEARCH Open Science Meeting.
- Work with the ARCSS Committee chair and the NSF ARCSS Program Director to plan for and implement longer-term synthesis efforts within the ARCSS Program.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

The work of the ARCSS Committee and the planning initiated by the new NSF ARCSS Program Director with the committee, have required additional coordination, communication, planning, and production of information to support the intensive efforts to initiate a major synthesis effort within the ARCSS Program and to implement several changes to the programmatic structure. These activities do not constitute a change in direction but the level of activity has increased.

2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop 2002

Accomplishments

- Worked with working group facilitators and presenters and the ARCSS Committee to synthesize recommendations from the workshop and make them available to the research community online for comment.
- Edited the ARCSS Committee's recommendations, the reports from each working group, compiled presentation and poster abstracts, and prepared for publication the proceedings from the February 2002 ARCSS Program All-Hands Workshop. The report is scheduled for publication in April 2003.

Projected Activities

- Publish and distribute the proceedings from the workshop, including presentation and poster abstracts, a summary of the recommendations from each working group, and the ARCSS Committee's analysis and synthesis of recommendations for further planning and implementation of ARCSS Program priorities.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

2.2.3 Coordinating a Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) Science Management Office

Accomplishments

- Planned and implemented a series of online workshops in April 2002 that focused on developing HARC proposals for new and emerging research initiatives. The first online workshop, which included 73 registered participants, focused on humans and Arctic hydrology and discussed HARC integration with the proposed pan-Arctic Community-wide Hydrological Analysis and Monitoring Program (Arctic-CHAMP). The second workshop, which included 65 registered participants, focused on integration with the ARCSS Nearshore and Coastal Processes initiative. Final reports from each workshop were posted on the HARC web site, along with transcripts of the workshop discussions.
- Revised the HARC web site to include information about additional HARC and HARC-like research projects.
- Arranged for HARC special issue of the journal *ARCTIC*. Solicited contributions from funded HARC researchers, most of which were submitted and reviewed in the past year. Work on the special issue is underway, although it will not be published until late 2003.
- Facilitated a HARC workshop at the Center for Global Change and Arctic System research at the University of Alaska Fairbanks in April 2002.
- Convened a HARC/Biocomplexity in the Environment: Coupled Human and natural Systems Workshop in November 2002, which, although funded separately from the cooperative agreement, clearly contributed to the coordination of research and integration activities conducted by the science management office and funded through the cooperative agreement with NSF.
- Initiated planning for a workshop on developing tools for integrated analysis in the context of human dimensions projects, scheduled for May 2003.

Projected Activities

- A workshop on integrated analysis of human dimensions research will be convened in May 2003. The study of systems requires the integration of disparate data sets to explain relationships between various components and processes of the system. This is especially challenging in human dimensions research, where social and environmental data must be examined together. At this time, a number of projects have carried out such work. Typically, each project has developed ad hoc solutions to integrated analysis, but a common set of analytical tools has not been developed. This workshop will examine the ways in which researchers have conducted an integrated analysis of quantitative data gathered in selected human dimensions research projects and will distinguish between methods of analysis that were available to researchers from prior work and ones that had to be developed for a given project. The need for further development of tools for integrated analysis will be determined and recommendations prepared to develop such tools.
- Work with the SMO director and HARC investigators to develop a list of reviewers who have the expertise to review coupled human-natural system proposals.
- Develop a one or two-page set of criteria spelling out *how* to review projects proposals for, and papers on, coupled human-natural system research.
- Develop a Human Dimensions conceptual model of the arctic system for use during the ARCSS program synthesis effort now underway.
- Prepare guidelines for researchers interested in developing HARC proposals on:
 - how to find an interdisciplinary project,
 - how to develop interdisciplinary teams, and,
 - how to write a HARC-type proposal.

- Develop a summary of “lessons learned” for conducting interdisciplinary research successfully.
- The information outlined will be prepared and distributed in a short publication and will be made available online through the HARC web site.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.2.4 Preparation and publication of CHAMP: *The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study*

Accomplishments

- Ongoing distribution of the report, including printed copies and electronically via the ARCUS web site.

Projected Activities

- Continue to distribute the report upon request, including printed copies and electronically via the ARCUS web site.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Community Conference

Accomplishments

- Discussed conference focus, goals, and timing with the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program Manager and initiated planning for a fall 2003 workshop on *Partnering with Arctic Communities*. Recommended that ARCUS plan and convene the conference in collaboration with the Alaska Native Science Commission (ANSC).
- Solicited ideas on the needs of arctic social sciences at arctic archeology conference in Pocatello, ID, in October and at American Anthropological Association meetings in New Orleans, LA, in November 2002.
- Discussed community needs and priorities with organizers of Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences (ICASS V).
- Updated several sections of *Arctic Social Sciences: Opportunities in Arctic Research*, first published in 1999. Prepared to publish a second edition of the report, pending approval of the updates from NSF.
- Initiated planning with the International Arctic Social Sciences Association (IASSA) secretariat located at the University of Alaska Fairbanks to implement a subcontract for the preliminary planning and coordination of the ICASS V to be held in Fairbanks, Alaska in May 2004.

Projected Activities

- Publish and distribute a second edition of *Arctic Social Sciences: Opportunities in Arctic Research*, a publication which is frequently requested by researchers and which is also used in many arctic social sciences courses.
- Select and convene, in collaboration with the ANSC, an organizing committee to plan *Partnering with Arctic Communities*.
- Identify timeline, main topics, keynote speakers, and invited participants.
- Announce the conference and publish a call for abstracts.

- Convene the conference in Fall 2003, bringing social scientists together with Arctic residents, students, and policy and decision-makers.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

The new NSF Arctic Social Sciences program manager decided in fall 2002 to postpone the conference originally scheduled for early 2003 in order to have time to assess needs and determine the most appropriate use of the conference funds in the context of her planning for the program.

2.3.2 Translation and publication of *Den Nye Sikkerhed - Groenland I Et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* (The New Security: Greenland in a Security Political Perspective)

Accomplishments

- Ongoing distribution of *Grønland i et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* at meetings, workshops, and by request.

Projected Activities

- Continue to distribute *Grønland i et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* at meetings, workshops, and by request.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.3.3 Preparation and Publication of *The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change*

Accomplishments

- Published 1,500 copies of *Earth is Faster Now* in time for a book launching reception at the Canadian Embassy in Washington, DC, in May 2002. Copies were distributed to member representatives and other attendees at the ARCUS 14th annual meeting. Smithsonian Institution funded printing of an extra 300 copies.
- Prepared a poster about the book for display at the ARCUS 14th annual meeting and Arctic Forum, at the AAAS meeting in Fairbanks in September 2002, and other venues.
- Held a book signing and reception at the Arctic Forum in May 2002.
- Developed a purchasing process including an order form, also available on line, and procedures for receiving and fulfilling orders.
- Distributed approximately 350 complimentary copies to book reviewers, chapter authors, and others.
- Individuals and bookstores have purchased over 300 copies of the book.

Projected Activities

- Continue marketing and distribution.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.4 ARCTIC NATURAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.4.1 Arctic Natural Sciences Program Materials

Accomplishments

- No activities in the past year.

Projected Activities

- No activities planned in the coming year.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities

A significant effort in ARCUS' arctic science education activities is the ongoing participation in a collaborative arctic science education project, *Eider Journey*, which provides research experiences for arctic students and teachers, in collaboration with several federal agencies and arctic communities. *Eider Journey* is a comprehensive education and stewardship program addressing issues of conservation and management of wildlife populations. Based around the threatened North American breeding population of Steller's eiders (*Political stelleri*), *Eider Journey* builds upon an existing collaboration among two entities of the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS)—Fairbanks Fish and Wildlife Office and Izembek National Wildlife Refuge, the Alaska North Slope Borough Department of Wildlife Management, the North Slope Borough School District, the Barrow Arctic Science Consortium (BASC), the NSF Office of Polar Programs through the funding support provided to ARCUS, and ARCUS.

The North American populations of Steller's eiders have been listed as a threatened species under the Endangered Species Act of 1973. The only known regularly occupied nesting area of Steller's eiders in North America is near Barrow, the largest rural community in Alaska. The community of Barrow is currently expanding into eider nesting areas, raising issues of human intrusion into preferred habitat.

To help Alaska's North Slope communities become more aware of the species' status and develop a protective attitude toward the local eider population, *Eider Journey* highlights the significance of the species through local partnerships and an education program that reflects local needs and community issues. The project engages both students and teachers in scientific research and provides training on field methods, analysis, and hypothesis testing. Activities initiated and supported by ARCUS include coordination of teacher and student participation with the research project and assistance in the development of educational materials. The collaborative work on *Eider Journey* also made possible funding from the National Fish and Wildlife Foundation to develop an educator's guide that will be used to support this and other arctic science education projects. *Eider Journey* exposes students to research that addresses issues of conservation and management of wildlife populations with four long-term goals:

1. Inform the public about Steller's eiders and involve communities in the decision-making processes related to eider conservation issues;
2. Provide first-hand experience in the field research that informs agency management decisions;
3. Promote sciences, particularly wildlife sciences, as a career; and
4. Provide quality resources and reliable information for educators and their students.

Accomplishments

- Each year since 1999, a USFWS research team has surveyed the eider pairs breeding in the Barrow area. In June 2002, four Barrow high school students assisted USFWS in the survey, covering approximately 180 square kilometers in and around the village of Barrow.
- Students were assigned to 3- or 4-person teams, responsible for searching a different area each day. Teams searched large areas on foot, recording and mapping all occurrences of Steller's or spectacled eiders, as well as predators such as gulls, jaegers, and foxes.
- Students learned to identify birds, orient and map using aerial photos, and classify habitat. The annual pair surveys provide data about the dramatic year-to-year changes in Steller's eider breeding as well as information on distribution of Steller's eiders in the Barrow area.
- In September 2002, a USFWS biologist, a Barrow science teacher, and the high school students traveled to Izembek National Wildlife Refuge. During the field trip, students worked with Peter McRoy of the Institute of Marine Science, University of Alaska Fairbanks, to learn about the Izembek Lagoon's eelgrass beds and their importance to eiders.
- The group collected and processed eelgrass samples and participated in banding eiders. Later, Dr. McRoy and USFWS staff traveled to Barrow to work with the students and help them summarize the data and prepare presentations to classes and the general public about what they had learned about eiders.

Other arctic science activities ARCUS has undertaken include:

- Worked with the Alaska Federation of Natives (AFN), the Alaska Native Knowledge Network (ANKN), and the University of Alaska Fairbanks in collaboration with the NSF-funded Rural Systemic Initiative (RSI), to compile integrated curricular materials and to make them available to a wide national audience and to provide technical assistance and training to RSI participants in Alaskan communities.
- Continued working with Arctic Native organizations and scientists to develop effective means by which the results of NSF-funded research can be returned to northern communities. ARCUS continues to develop relationships, resources, and expertise in this area.
- Continued to distribute a four-page insert to *Witness the Arctic* that provides information and advice to researchers on developing appropriate and useful science education projects, including information about education on global climate change, indigenous knowledge, and tips on bringing research into the classroom.
- Continued to support and promote the development and successful implementation of arctic science education projects by sharing information and expertise, supporting communicative networks, and distributing information about results and opportunities.
- Presented information about science education projects and opportunities at research community seminars, such as the University of Alaska –Center for Global Change information series.

Projected Activities

- Expand the *Eider Journey* Educator's Guide to include lessons and background material focused on the North Slope of Alaska natural history, coastal ecosystems, and other aspects of the North Slope environment. Include curriculum development and design work for publication of guide. The education guide provides both information and activities that incorporate the concepts of endangered and threatened species, stewardship, and ecological principles. The guide can be used in conjunction with field trips or as part of a regular classroom study.

- ARCUS and the USFWS plan to continue the *Eider Journey* in 2003 and are seeking additional funding from sources other than NSF. In future years, the program may bring students from the Alaska Peninsula to participate in fieldwork in Barrow.
- Develop an *Eider Journey* web page, in collaboration with student participants.
- Provide curriculum materials from arctic science education projects, such as Arctic Alive and the *Eider Journey* education guide, to Eisenhower Clearinghouse (<http://enc.org>) for access by more educators around the US.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS implemented an Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series in January 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community and to nurture better understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents.

Accomplishments

- Advertised the Series on-line, at meetings, and through *Witness the Arctic*.
- From April 2002 to March 2003, eight speakers have participated in the Series, addressing arctic issues at thirteen different public engagements. Topics covered included native languages, arctic folklore and literature, arctic policy, ecology, and reindeer herding techniques.
- Speakers presented at a variety of public venues including libraries, classrooms, and on the radio, as well as at graduate seminars and conferences.
- The Arctic Visiting Speakers Series' (AVS) web site was revised and updated and includes all the presentations by year as well as "current tours".
- The AVS web pages are easier to navigate for people seeking presenters. An AVS speaker is highlighted on the ARCUS home page.
- Five speakers have been added to the Speaker's Bureau, and it now includes profiles for 29 potential Arctic Visiting Speakers. Eleven additional entries have been received for the Speakers' Bureau but have not yet been added to the online database.
- Two speakers traveled from other countries to speak in the U.S.; Two U.S. researchers traveled to other countries. Four U.S. speakers visited institutions within the U.S.

Projected Activities

- Continue to promote the use of the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series to promote collaboration and information sharing about arctic research and the Arctic, including by distributing information via Arctic Info and in *Witness the Arctic*.
- Advertise the AVS series more extensively among Arctic residents and encourage participation by indigenous experts as visiting speakers and by Arctic communities as host institutions.
- Post the AVS information to several educational list serves around the country to stimulate interest from the K-12 education community to apply as host institutions.
- Support up to ten speaker tours in the next year.
- Continue to recruit individuals for the Speakers Bureau, although host institutions are not restricted to inviting speakers from the Speakers' Bureau.

- Post updated information about speaker tours on the ARCUS web site, including presentation videos and other materials sent to ARCUS by host institutions and speakers.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

3.3 Arctic Science Education Report

ARCUS convened a 15-member working group of selected researchers, educators, students, and arctic community representatives in March 2000 to review various programs and educational approaches to science education and to prepare recommendations for the development of research-experience-based science education programs for the Arctic. The previous ARCUS cooperative agreement funded development of the report and circulation of the draft for community review.

Accomplishments

- Distributed 600 printed copies and made the report and its recommendations available electronically through the ARCUS web site.
- All available copies have been distributed but we continue to receive many requests for this report.

Projected Activities

- Continue to make the report available electronically and to distribute “Xeroxed” copies upon request.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

3.3 ARCTIC ALIVE!

In September 2001, ARCUS was awarded funding through the National Science Foundation – Directorate for Geosciences, to develop and implement a pilot distance-delivery education program. Arctic Alive! allows students to “participate” in arctic research without ever leaving their classrooms. This program is based on a very successful program developed by Heurisko Ltd. in New Zealand, called, LEARNZ. Although not funded through the cooperative agreement, the 2002 pilot program is described below in some detail, because the second year of Arctic Alive! will be partially funded through the cooperative agreement.

Arctic Alive! allows students to interact with researchers in remote arctic locations by using a variety of technologies. Through these technologies and corresponding curriculum, classrooms can simultaneously investigate the Arctic, discover careers in science, and research this unique and exciting world right along with the experts.

The April 2002 “virtual field trip” was located outside of Barrow, Alaska. This first “virtual field trip” focused on geoscience research and examined the arctic climate, sea ice and climate change. Patrick Lovely, a Fairbanks teacher and biologist, was hired to be a “virtual” liaison and guide for the students while he accompanied the sea ice researchers. Over the course of 5 days, students learned about albedo transect research, ice core research, and ice core data analysis from researchers Don Perovich, Tom Grenfell, Hajo Eicken, and Andrew Mahoney. They also heard from Barrow community members, Richard Glenn and Harry Brower, and wildlife biologist, Craig George, to get their perspectives on climate change.

Accomplishments

- Five classrooms (grades 6-9) and three home school families from across Alaska participated in 2002. The 2002 program was a pilot, and the number of schools allowed to participate was limited. The primary goal of the pilot project was to develop and test a variety of methods for teachers and students to participate and receive a comprehensive program. The technology was deliberately kept simple so that everyone that wanted to participate could do so with only a speakerphone and an Internet connection. To do this, the following were developed:
 - a comprehensive web site that included secure areas for teachers and students to access all materials and resources;
 - complete on-line lesson plans that included many relevant resources so teachers and students didn't have to search for related resources;
 - lessons that could be used individually or as a unit and that meet Alaska state and national content standards in science, technology, and math;
 - an on-line discussion forum where students and researchers could interact;
 - downloadable Word and PDF files of all the materials;
 - free access to daily audio-conference calls where students and researchers were able to interact in real-time;
 - audio files of the conference calls in case classrooms were unable to participate in the audio conferences.
 - Online curriculum materials and audio files are available to classrooms that were unable to participate in the virtual field trip in real-time.
- An audio conference was held each day of the field trip between the researchers and students. Audio-conference calls were selected as the main method of communication between the students and researchers due to the availability of phones in the classroom and the potential absence of more sophisticated communication technologies. The students asked questions that were then answered by the researchers.
- The Arctic Alive teacher also posted a daily diary and photos of the expedition in the discussion forum. Both the audio-conference calls and the forum proved to be an easy way for students to participate and talk to the researchers. The actual web site served as a great resource for additional information and lesson planning.
- Teachers and students evaluated the project following the completion of the field trip and classroom activities. Evaluations were positive and encouraged continued development of the program.

Projected Activities

- Edit the 2002 curriculum materials for printing and distribution to educators.
- One of the two planned April 2003 Arctic Alive! field trips will be supported through the cooperative agreement. This field trip, *The 2003 Ecological Change Expedition*, will focus on ecological research in Kotzebue Sound, Alaska and will include information on using traditional knowledge as well as western scientific research practices.
- Develop new curriculum materials, activities, and resources for the 2003 Ecological Change Expedition.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

4.1 *Witness the Arctic*: Chronicles of the Arctic Science Research Program

Accomplishments

- Published and distributed 8,850 copies of a 28-page issue of *Witness* in July 2002 (Spring 2002, Volume 9, Number 2) plus a four-page insert on arctic research at Louisiana State University, a four-page Arctic Section and ARCSS address insert,

and a four-page ARCUS address insert. The newsletter feature story was titled "*Ancient Ice, Cool Science* Brings the Public Face to Face with Climate Change Research in the North."

- Published and distributed 9,000 copies of *Witness* (Spring 2003, Volume 10, Number 1) in March 2003. This issue is a 36-page newsletter with a feature story that provides an overview of the first field season of the Shelf-Basin Interactions project.
- Published on-line editions of the newsletters on ARCUS' web site, <http://www.arcus.org>.

Projected Activities

- Solicit and edit contributions and prepare for publication the Autumn 2003 issue of *Witness* (Volume 10, Number 2), which will be published in October 2003.
- Begin work on the Spring 2004 issue of *Witness* (Volume 11, Number 1), which will be published in March 2004.
- Publish on-line edition of the newsletter on ARCUS' web site, <http://www.arcus.org>.
- Initiate a mailing list review to eliminate any outdated addresses or duplication. The mailing list database is monitored carefully but over time problems like this can increase the mailing list size beyond the actual readership.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

The number of newsletter subscribers continues to increase with each issue, with commensurate increases in printing and distribution costs. Printing and paper costs also have increased in the last several years. A new distribution method was used in the past year, which resulted in some cost savings and more efficient distribution.

4.2 Web Site/Internet Resources

Accomplishments

- Continuous development and maintenance of the over 7,000-page ARCUS web site to provide:
 - Sources of information for the general public about arctic research.
 - A forum for scientific exchange among arctic researchers.
 - Suggestions for integration into educational programs.
 - Access to other researchers, programs, and stakeholders working in the Arctic.
 - Viable ways to inform and involve arctic residents in research activities.
 - Information about progress and recommendations related to various arctic research initiatives, including projects coordinated by ARCUS as well as other organizations.
- An update of the webserver software provided added security and stability for the ARCUS website. As a result, however, many of the site's web forms, which allow users to register for workshops, subscribe to newsletters, etc. also had to be upgraded to be compatible with the new server software. These upgrades and revisions have resulted in a better user interface and easier management.
- Initiated a redesign of several sections of the web site to improve search functions, information delivery, and ease of information management, including the general education site and the Arctic Visiting Speakers' site.
- Initiated a redesign of the interface and database backbone for the Directory of Arctic Researchers, the Calendar, Arctic Info to resolve problems in the database code, improve search capability and speed, and to update the user interface.
- Posted draft reports related to arctic research activities, making them available for community review.
- Posted on-line versions of various arctic research publications, including all documents prepared by ARCUS, for easy access and downloading.

- Created, maintained, and updated sections of the web site for various ARCUS-facilitated programs, meetings and workshops as mentioned under other activity descriptions in this report.
- Provided links to numerous other arctic organizations' research sites, databases, planning processes, and other information of interest to the arctic research community.
- Provided support and consultation for the development of Internet resources by other institutions and organizations working with arctic research or arctic science education, including IASC and the Alaska Native Science Commission.

Projected Activities

- Initiate a major redesign of several sections of the web site to improve search functions, information delivery, and ease of information management, including the publication download section, Hot Links, the site index and search pages, and several of the science planning activity sections.
- Continue to maintain, manage, and update this very large and frequently updated web site.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.3 Arctic Info Listserve

Accomplishments

- Received, reviewed, accepted or declined, edited, and formatted over 350 submissions for the Arctic Info listserv in the past year.
- Communicated with subscribers regarding postings, special information requests, non-automated subscribe or unsubscribe requests, and other concerns.
- Maintained database of subscribers in order to analyze use and areas of interest.
- Provided general information on the demographics of the subscriber list to several organizations and individuals interested in using the list to announce information to the research community.
- Distributed 300 Arctic Info messages from April 2002 through March 2003.
- The listserv has 4,310 current subscribers, an increase of over 455 subscribers in the past year.

Projected Activities

- Continue advertising, maintenance, and management of the listserv. Switch from current listserv software to a more user friendly, less annoying and anxiety provoking list management software.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.4 The Directory of Arctic Researchers

Accomplishments

- Added new records for a total of 3,590 as of March 2003.
- Surveyed researchers with current directory records to get updated contact and current research information.
- Surveyed significant international research organizations and individuals to expand non-U.S. researcher records in the database.

- Maintained and regularly updated a downloadable PDF of the Directory including alphabetically listed individual researcher entries and a cross-reference file listing researchers by name within science specialty categories.
- Provided subsets of directory information in response to requests from the Canadian Polar Commission, the International Glaciological Society, the University Corporation for Atmospheric Research, and the Global Hydrology and Climate Center.

Projected Activities

- Continuing maintenance and expansion of the on-line version of the directory. Initiate a survey process to include arctic science administrators at Alaska State agencies, federal agencies, and arctic science education resources.
- Upgrade hardware and software to keep pace with information technology improvements.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.5 Internet Graphics Archive

Accomplishments

- Developed metadata structure and process for collecting information from providers about photos, figures, and other graphics made available through the Internet Graphics Archive.
- Developed a draft legal contract for contributions to the archive, which defines levels of permitted use, and any required payment, attribution, or acknowledgement.
- Identified a set of photos and graphics to use as a pilot to prepare meta-data, secure permissions, and make available in the online archive.
- Developed “draft” online interface for the graphics archive and performed in-house testing.

Projected Activities

- Obtain use permissions and attribution for the remainder of ARCUS’ existing photo collection.
- Further develop the online interface that makes photos available while protecting copyrights and requiring attribution for any resources used.
- Refine the online graphic and photo archive search capabilities.
- Identify or produce additional figures, cartoons, photographs, and maps depicting arctic research-related information and make this information available through the archive on the ARCUS Web site.
- Continue to develop short abstracts that explain each graphic simply and clearly and that provide information necessary for attribution, as well as citations for source material and other related references.
- Continue developing contracts with providers to define legal use of photos and figures.
- Make graphics available for downloading and printing from the ARCUS Web site through a searchable database and PDF format.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

Accomplishments

- Planned and hosted a two-day *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with ARCUS' 14th Annual Meeting in Arlington, VA in May 2002, attended by 90 participants, including arctic researchers from the U.S. and other countries, policy makers, federal agency personnel, and Arctic residents. The *Forum* focused on biocomplexity in the Arctic. Dr. Rita Colwell, the director of the National Science Foundation, delivered the keynote presentation.
- The *Arctic Forum* in 2002 featured twenty-one arctic research projects in oral presentations and 14 posters. Featured projects included research funded by NSF, arctic research supported by other federal agencies or programs, and significant international arctic research efforts.
- Printed and distributed 750 copies of the proceedings from the 2002 *Arctic Forum*.
- Developed information resources regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities and participated in outreach activities at scientific meetings and workshops to inform the broader scientific community and key policy and decisions-makers about important arctic research efforts and findings.
- Participated or sponsored Arctic outreach activities at the Fall Meeting of AGU in 2002, at Coalition for National Science Funding sessions throughout the year, and at other relevant meetings and workshops.

Projected Activities

- Convene a two-day *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with ARCUS' 15th Annual Meeting in Arlington, VA in April 2003. The focus of the *Arctic Forum* 2003 will be Responding to Global Change: Resilience and Vulnerability in the Arctic Systems.
- Keynote speakers will include Dr. James R. Mahoney, Director of the United States Climate Change Science Program, who will speak about The U.S. Climate Change Science Program and its Relevance to the Arctic. Mahoney is the Assistant Secretary of Commerce for Oceans and Atmosphere and Deputy NOAA Administrator. The other keynote speaker will be Dr. Gordon Orians, chair of the National Research Council Committee on Cumulative Environmental Effects of Oil and Gas Activities on Alaska's North Slope, who will speak on the cumulative effects of oil and gas activities on the physical, biological, and human systems of the region. Orians is Professor Emeritus of Zoology at the University of Washington. He was elected to the National Academy of Sciences in 1989 and has served as chair of the Board of Environmental Studies and Toxicology since 1997.
- Print and distribute the *Arctic Forum 2003* abstract volume.
- Prepare posters or presentations on request and participate in major scientific meetings or workshops to provide information and outreach regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.7 Publication: The Arctic

Many members of the arctic research community have expressed a need for an introduction to the environments and peoples of the Arctic that is scientifically accurate while remaining comprehensible to the general public, including middle and high school students. To address this need, ARCUS began developing an overview of the arctic region for a general audience in 2001, with funding through the previous cooperative agreement with NSF. Tentatively titled *The Arctic: Changes in a Polar Region*, this book is similar to a magazine in the quality of graphics

and level of complexity and will be accessible to a wide range of readers. The contents and the publication design and layout are targeted to the general public and middle and high school students. The contents cover ocean, terrestrial, and human components of the Arctic and review various aspects of these domains, including contemporary and historical research, through a seasonal framework. Links among important arctic processes and between the biophysical systems and human cultures are illustrated.

Accomplishments

- In January 2001 the draft publication was circulated for review by a group of educators, arctic researchers, and experts in science information development. The reviews provided substantive guidance for the difficult task of describing diverse and complex processes simply and clearly.

Projected Activities

- Conduct an invited review by several Arctic experts and further revise several important sections of the publication.
- Research and purchase photo rights for photos selected for the final publication.
- Prepare final versions of special graphics for publication.
- Publish in December 2003 and make the initial print run of 5,000 copies available for public information requests and educational uses. The publication also will be available electronically via the ARCUS web site.
- ARCUS plans to market this publication so that additional copies can be printed upon demand without securing additional funding from NSF.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Because of the amount of work still required to create a publication of the quality considered necessary by ARCUS, NSF, and the research community, completion of this publication was postponed to the latter half of the third year of the cooperative agreement in order to direct staff resources to other more urgently needed projects.

4.8 Eider Endangered Species Consultation Bulletin

Accomplishments

- The draft consultation bulletin, which was developed during the first year of the cooperative agreement, was reviewed and approved by USFWS staff in the Endangered Species Division and was also sent to the Alaska North Slope Borough Department of Wildlife Management and the Barrow Arctic Science Consortium for review and comment.
- Revisions were made to the bulleting in accordance with the review comments received.
- The consultation bulletin was forwarded to NSF Arctic Sciences Section for discussion.

Projected Activities

- None expected at this time.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

ARCUS had expected that when the process of developing the bulletin was completed and the consultation bulletin finally approved, copies would be made available as a downloadable PDF linked from various web sites providing research support and logistics information to arctic researchers, as well as being available as a photocopied handout. No further word on this project has been received from Arctic Sciences Section staff, however.

5. Core Support

Core support provides management and infrastructure crucial to support all major tasks and the projects and activities included in each task through the cooperative agreement. This category was initiated at the recommendation of the NSF program officer, who suggested that stability and continuity would be achieved more effectively by defining a category to support direct activities that support the whole of the cooperative agreement that would not be vulnerable to the changes in the specific tasks and activities funded from year-to-year through the agreement.

ARCUS is a relatively small non-profit organization and the Executive Director is intimately involved in all activities of the organization including planning, prioritizing, managing, and directly implementing the work undertaken on behalf of the National Science Foundation. The Executive Director works closely with ARCUS project managers to prioritize tasks with respect to annual and longer-term plans and to manage individual workloads and projects. She closely reviews activities and products and ensures that projects are completed as scheduled and in accordance with the annual plan and that the products or effects of the activities are beneficial to arctic research and to the goals of the particular task funded through the cooperative agreement. She is directly involved in working with outside committees and contributors to ensure that projects are concluded effectively and in a timely fashion. The Executive Director also works closely with the ARCUS Business Manager in budgeting and reviewing ongoing project expenditures against the NSF budget. The Executive Director liaises directly with NSF on all planning, programmatic, and budget issues. This component of management is essential to the ongoing work ARCUS carries out on behalf of NSF.

Similarly, the Systems Administrator manages the network, server, and all technical needs required to support NSF tasks and sub-tasks. He works directly with the Executive Director to ensure that all hardware and software requirements are met so that server and network operations supporting NSF activities are carried out smoothly and efficiently. The Executive Director and Systems Administrator plan for upcoming needs, including scientific meetings and conferences convened by ARCUS on behalf of the NSF, in conjunction with the annual plan.

While the work of both these positions is directly related to the successful implementation of NSF activities and projects, it is more difficult to allocate much of this time specifically to any one individual project, hence the use of Core Support to collect these direct overarching management and infrastructure costs. Other costs charged to Core Support include direct system infrastructure (computer hardware and software required to maintain the network and server needed to support the database and listserver, NSF sponsored tasks), high-speed Internet, and the development necessary to continuously maintain the level of service committed to the Arctic research community under the cooperative agreement.

Accomplishments

- Coordinated planning, managed emerging priorities, and supervised work on all the tasks and sub-tasks described in this report. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category.
- Upgraded hardware, software, and programming to expand capability for several projects that require expanded server, network, and database capacity, support for NSF-sponsored meeting online registration, poster submission, and general information and the development of a site featuring Arctic relevant news items and information of interest to the media.
- Managed the server setup, the network, the creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category.

- Supported staff training to increase technical expertise for programming and managing database backbone for all database-driven functions of the ARCUS web site, which serves the Directory of Arctic Researchers, the ALIAS web site, Arctic Info, the Calendar, and support for NSF-sponsored meeting online registration, poster submission, and general information.
- Supported staff travel to arctic research meetings and workshops that addressed topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which were not specific to one project.

Projected Activities

- Coordinate planning, prioritization and supervision of work on all the tasks and projects described in the projected activities, the program plan and budget for 2003-2004. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- Continue to research and upgrade hardware, software and programming required to expand the capability of such projects as the Directory of Arctic Researchers, the ALIAS website, Arctic Info, the Calendar, the media site, and NSF online program discussions, meeting registrations and poster submissions, and general information.
- Manage the server setup, the network, the creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to direct activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- Support staff participation at arctic research meetings and workshops on topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which are not specific to one project.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
OPP-0101279
Total Costs by Category

Attachment A

5/12/03 14:17

	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	YEAR 2 Actuals thru 1/03 Projections thru 03/03	Year 2 Funds Remaining	Proposed YEAR 3 BUDGET
1 ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING					
1.1 Arctic Logistics	276,800	19,067	60,593	23,065	29,019
1.2 ALIAS Website	601,812	96,470	156,089	(41,358)	143,747
1.3 GIS Planning	35,561	35,461	100	(100)	-
1.4 SEARCH Planning	271,171	-	15,899	(1,754)	255,273
1.5 Bering Sea Planning	88,920	-	43,255	(43,255)	45,665
1.6 Workshop TBD	136,474	-	-	-	-
1.7 SEARCH Brochure	5,741	5,741	-	-	-
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,416,478	156,738	275,936	(63,402)	473,704
Indirect Costs	606,795	65,922	117,838	(26,448)	203,693
TOTAL	2,023,273	222,660	393,774	(89,850)	677,397
2 NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION					
2.1 Arctic Section Science Materials	24,307	7,040	17,268	345	-
2.2 ARCSS Program Coordination					
2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination	516,409	30,274	144,126	(26,192)	247,947
2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop	308,640	259,825	41,744	(3,859)	-
2.2.3 HARC SMO	151,760	44,449	34,580	30,923	72,731
2.2.4 Arctic Hydrology Report	18,296	18,276	19	(19)	-
SubTotal 2.2 Direct Costs	995,105	352,824	220,469	852	320,678
2.3 ASSP Program Coordination					
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Workshop	138,479	6,466	67,133	(2,300)	64,880
2.3.2 Greenland Book	12,263	12,263	-	-	-
2.3.3 The Earth is Faster Now	38,664	15,933	22,731	8,431	-
SubTotal 2.3 Direct Costs	189,406	34,662	89,864	6,131	64,880
2.4 ANS Program Coordination					
2.4.1 ANS materials	20,108	-	-	-	-
Sub-Total Direct Costs	1,228,926	394,525	327,601	7,328	385,558
Indirect Costs	462,950	165,313	103,282	17,167	142,220
TOTAL	1,691,876	559,838	430,883	24,495	527,778
3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION					
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	82,333	10,847	12,200	2,762	
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers Program	158,884	37,130	21,812	16,629	27,907
3.3 Arctic Science Education Report	22,943	7,691	15,252	(15,252)	-
3.4 ARCTIC ALIVE!	-	-	-	-	27,974
SubTotal Direct Costs	264,160	55,668	49,264	4,140	55,881
Indirect Costs	112,668	23,410	20,789	2,174	24,029
TOTAL	376,828	79,079	70,053	6,314	79,910
4 INFORMATION AND OUTREACH					
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletter	362,565	53,943	93,706	(903)	88,520
4.2 Web Site/Internet Resources	325,873	68,740	53,579	13,445	63,295
4.3 Arctic Info Listserver	92,286	12,508	13,224	3,462	16,852
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	50,568	8,087	16,868	(4,422)	7,772
4.5 Internet Graphics Archive	74,076	-	13,922	1,329	26,762
4.6 Community Outreach	236,535	46,871	55,201	(3,775)	45,956
4.7 Publication: The Arctic	40,715	619	55	47,854	40,041
4.8 Endangered Species Consultation Bulletin	2,617	2,150	468	(468)	-
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,185,235	192,917	247,022	56,522	289,198
Indirect Costs	504,008	81,074	104,607	23,767	122,205
TOTAL	1,689,243	273,991	351,629	80,289	411,403
5 CORE SUPPORT					
Core Support					
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,423,532	262,598	212,918	103,053	295,564
Indirect Costs	608,415	110,337	90,431	45,437	127,093
TOTAL	2,031,947	372,935	303,349	148,490	422,657
TOTAL COSTS	7,813,167	1,508,501	1,549,689	169,738	2,119,145

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	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	YEAR 2 Actuals thru 1/03 Projections thru 03/03	YEAR 2 Funds Remaining	Proposed YEAR 3 BUDGET
1 Arctic Community Science Planning					
1.1 ARCTIC LOGISTICS					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	100,490	9,479	25,927	(3,112)	12,610
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	25,678	4,127	5,231	1,077	3,204
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	80,847	2,634	6,468	20,632	3,807
Other Direct Costs	69,784	2,828	22,967	4,468	9,398
Total direct costs	276,800	19,067	60,593	23,065	29,019
Indirect Costs	118,717	8,016	25,931	10,042	12,478
Total direct and indirect costs	395,516	27,083	86,524	33,107	41,498
1.2 ALIAS WEBSITE					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	423,571	60,048	89,479	(10,018)	101,527
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	77,635	14,437	14,388	1,382	16,020
Travel (foreign)	5,747	-	5,747	(5,747)	-
Participant Support Costs	1,254	-	1,254	(1,254)	-
Other Direct Costs	93,606	21,985	45,221	(25,721)	26,200
Total direct costs	601,812	96,470	156,089	(41,358)	143,747
Indirect Costs	257,138	40,532	66,428	(17,093)	61,811
Total direct and indirect costs	858,951	137,002	222,517	(58,452)	205,558
1.3 GIS PLANNING					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	20,920	20,920	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	2,294	2,294	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	8,050	8,050	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	4,296	4,196	100	(100)	-
Total direct costs	35,561	35,461	100	(100)	-
Indirect Costs	14,997	14,954	43	(43)	-
Total direct and indirect costs	50,558	50,415	143	(143)	-
1.4 SEARCH PLANNING					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	81,374	-	6,801	2,190	74,573
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic and foreign)	21,581	-	5,561	(2,407)	16,020
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	59,640	-	-	-	59,640
Other Direct Costs	108,577	-	3,537	(1,537)	105,040
Total direct costs	271,171	-	15,899	(1,754)	255,273
Indirect Costs	116,604	-	6,836	(754)	109,767
Total direct and indirect costs	387,775	-	22,735	(2,508)	365,040
1.5 BERING SEA PLANNING					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	40,322	-	11,259	(11,259)	29,063
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	5,371	-	3,769	(3,769)	1,602
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	18,817	-	18,817	(18,817)	-
Other Direct Costs	24,411	-	9,411	(9,411)	15,000
Total direct costs	88,921	-	43,256	(43,256)	45,665
Indirect Costs	38,236	-	18,600	(18,600)	19,636
Total direct and indirect costs	127,157	-	61,856	(61,856)	65,301
1.6 WKSP TBD					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	37,691	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	6,558	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	65,325	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	26,900	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	136,474	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	58,684	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	195,157	-	-	-	-

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	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	YEAR 2 Actuals thru 1/03 Projections thru 03/03	YEAR 2 Funds Remaining	Proposed YEAR 3 BUDGET
1.7 SEARCH BROCHURE					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,090	1,090	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	4,652	4,652	-	-	-
Total direct costs	5,741	5,741	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	2,420	2,420	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	8,161	8,161	-	-	-

2 NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination

2.1 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	10,858	6,799	4,060	5,053	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	13,449	241	13,208	(4,708)	-
Total direct costs	24,307	7,040	17,268	345	-
Indirect Costs	10,372	2,947	7,425	148	-
Total direct and indirect costs	34,680	9,987	24,693	493	-

2.2 ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.2.1 ARCSS COORDINATION

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	118,361	9,127	30,094	(1,542)	51,974
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	41,428	4,244	14,493	(8,973)	11,214
Travel (foreign)	12,015	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	200,316	10,677	49,024	(35,474)	104,280
Other Direct Costs	144,290	6,226	50,515	19,796	80,479
Total direct costs	516,409	30,274	144,126	(26,192)	247,947
Indirect Costs	182,720	12,681	46,544	(19,402)	83,048
Total direct and indirect costs	699,129	42,955	190,670	(45,594)	330,995

2.2.2 ARCSS ALL-HANDS WORKSHOP

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	72,617	46,331	19,215	(4,946)	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	16,887	17,182	(294)	294	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	90,513	89,230	1,284	71	-
Other Direct Costs	128,623	107,083	21,539	721	-
Total direct costs	308,640	259,825	41,744	(3,859)	-
Indirect Costs	129,527	108,766	17,720	(1,430)	-
Total direct and indirect costs	438,167	368,591	59,464	(5,289)	-

2.2.3 HARC SMO

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	43,783	20,151	8,485	3,071	15,147
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	9,952	1,249	2,295	2,436	6,408
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	16,163	1,686	2,548	10,646	11,928
Other Direct Costs	81,862	21,363	21,252	14,770	39,248
Total direct costs	151,760	44,449	34,580	30,923	72,731
Indirect Costs	64,631	18,656	14,701	13,465	31,274
Total direct and indirect costs	216,391	63,105	49,281	44,388	104,005

2.2.4 ARCTIC HYDROLOGY REPORT

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	16,279	16,279	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	2,017	1,997	19	(19)	-
Total direct costs	18,296	18,276	19	(19)	-
Indirect Costs	7,704	7,696	8	(8)	-
Total direct and indirect costs	25,999	25,972	27	(27)	-

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	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	YEAR 2 Actuals thru 1/03 Projections thru 03/03	YEAR 2 Funds Remaining	Proposed YEAR 3 BUDGET
2.3 ASSP PROGRAM COORDINATION					
2.3.1 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES WORKSHOP					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	25,692	6,166	4,325	12,271	15,201
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	6,491	46	3,241	(87)	3,204
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	31,725	-	-	31,100	31,725
Other Direct Costs	74,571	254	59,568	(45,584)	14,750
Total direct costs	138,479	6,466	67,133	(2,300)	64,880
Indirect Costs	37,991	2,727	7,366	20,513	27,898
Total direct and indirect costs	176,470	9,192	74,499	18,213	92,778
2.3.2 GREENLAND BOOK					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,326	1,326	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	10,937	10,937	-	-	-
Total direct costs	12,263	12,263	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	5,172	5,172	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	17,435	17,435	-	-	-
2.3.3 THE EARTH IS FASTER NOW					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	7,781	2,733	5,047	1,298	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,556	-	1,556	21	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	3,548	-
Participant Support Costs	2,380	-	2,380	(380)	-
Other Direct Costs	26,948	13,200	13,748	3,944	-
Total direct costs	38,664	15,933	22,731	8,431	-
Indirect Costs	16,186	6,668	9,518	3,881	-
Total direct and indirect costs	54,851	22,601	32,249	12,312	-
2.4 ANS PROGRAM COORDINATION					
2.4.1 ANS MATERIALS					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	11,808	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	8,300	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	20,108	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	8,647	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	28,755	-	-	-	-
3 Arctic Science Education					
3.1 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION ACTIVITIES					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	20,991	8,181	6,492	(3,712)	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	7,297	739	-	3,154	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	8,387	-	548	3,185	-
Other Direct Costs	17,684	1,927	5,161	136	-
Total direct costs	54,359	10,847	12,200	2,762	-
Indirect Costs	23,213	4,561	5,189	1,245	-
Total direct and indirect costs	77,572	15,408	17,389	4,008	-
3.2 ARCTIC VISITING SPEAKERS PROGRAM					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	37,643	9,599	7,301	1,440	8,107
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	120,889	27,301	14,388	15,312	19,800
Other Direct Costs	353	230	123	(123)	-
Total direct costs	158,884	37,130	21,812	16,629	27,907
Indirect Costs	67,804	15,611	9,217	7,312	12,000
Total direct and indirect costs	226,688	52,741	31,029	23,942	39,907

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	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	YEAR 2 Actuals thru 1/03 Projections thru 03/03	YEAR 2 Funds Remaining	Proposed YEAR 3 BUDGET
3.3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION REPORT					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	9,849	7,691	2,158	(2,158)	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	13,094	-	13,094	(13,094)	-
Total direct costs	22,943	7,691	15,252	(15,252)	-
Indirect Costs	9,622	3,239	6,383	(6,383)	-
Total direct and indirect costs	32,565	10,930	21,635	(21,635)	-

3.4 ARCTIC ALIVE

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	20,420	-	-	-	20,420
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,204	-	-	-	3,204
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	4,350	-	-	-	4,350
Total direct costs	27,974	-	-	-	27,974
Indirect Costs	12,029	-	-	-	12,029
Total direct and indirect costs	40,003	-	-	-	40,003

4 Information and Outreach

4.1 WITNESS THE ARCTIC NEWSLETTERS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	138,197	22,734	34,526	(3,314)	38,420
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	4,073	794	-	1,577	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	220,294	30,414	59,180	834	50,100
Total direct costs	362,565	53,943	93,706	(903)	88,520
Indirect Costs	154,853	22,642	39,797	108	38,063
Total direct and indirect costs	517,417	76,585	133,504	(795)	126,583

4.2 INTERNET RESOURCES

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	300,362	52,897	46,410	13,614	60,795
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,070	1,740	1,330	(1,330)	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	22,441	14,102	5,839	1,161	2,500
Total direct costs	325,873	68,740	53,579	13,445	63,295
Indirect Costs	139,178	28,891	22,758	6,062	27,217
Total direct and indirect costs	465,050	97,631	76,337	19,507	90,511

4.3 ARCTIC INFO LISTSERVER

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	87,868	12,430	11,384	3,702	14,352
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	4,418	78	1,840	(240)	2,500
Total direct costs	92,286	12,508	13,224	3,462	16,852
Indirect Costs	39,475	5,255	5,601	1,574	7,246
Total direct and indirect costs	131,760	17,763	18,826	5,035	24,098

4.4 DIRECTORY OF ARCTIC RESEARCHERS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	31,401	7,899	4,668	3,278	5,272
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,279	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	15,888	188	12,200	(7,700)	2,500
Total direct costs	50,568	8,087	16,868	(4,422)	7,772
Indirect Costs	21,498	3,401	7,083	(1,731)	3,342
Total direct and indirect costs	72,065	11,489	23,951	(6,153)	11,114

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4.5 INTERNET GRAPHICS ARCHIVE					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	48,130	-	7,976	(225)	21,762
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	25,946	-	5,946	1,554	5,000
Total direct costs	74,076	-	13,922	1,329	26,762
Indirect Costs	31,785	-	5,919	639	11,508
Total direct and indirect costs	105,862	-	19,841	1,967	38,270

4.6 ARCTIC COMMUNITY OUTREACH

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	71,921	13,743	14,590	(2,116)	15,248
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	20,941	1,417	-	6,308	6,408
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	36,758	2,356	9,112	(982)	8,280
Other Direct Costs	106,915	29,356	31,500	(6,985)	16,020
Total direct costs	236,535	46,871	55,202	(3,775)	45,956
Indirect Costs	100,774	19,725	23,230	(1,117)	19,761
Total direct and indirect costs	337,309	66,596	78,432	(4,891)	65,717

4.7 PUBLICATION: THE ARCTIC

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	16,440	344	55	23,854	16,042
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	24,275	275	-	24,000	24,000
Total direct costs	40,715	619	55	47,854	40,042
Indirect Costs	15,351	260	23	18,428	15,068
Total direct and indirect costs	56,066	879	77	66,282	55,110

4.8 ENDANGERED SPECIES CONSULTATION BULLETIN

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,617	2,150	468	(468)	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	2,617	2,150	468	(468)	-
Indirect Costs	1,095	900	196	(196)	-
Total direct and indirect costs	3,712	3,049	663	(663)	-

5 Core Support

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	957,689	157,403	140,593	59,821	189,919
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	76,327	11,770	10,867	6,480	17,622
Travel (foreign)	7,322	-	-	2,365	2,403
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	382,193	93,425	61,458	34,387	85,620
Total direct costs	1,423,531	262,598	212,918	103,053	295,564
Indirect Costs	608,415	110,337	90,431	45,437	127,093
Total direct and indirect costs	2,031,946	372,935	303,349	148,490	422,657

TOTAL PROGRAMS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,757,490	495,519	481,312	86,721	690,431
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	333,622	60,039	62,436	6,164	84,906
Travel (foreign)	25,084	-	5,747	166	2,403
Participant Support Costs	741,062	141,933	105,822	24,039	239,460
Other Direct Costs	1,661,073	364,955	457,424	(9,449)	482,705
Total direct costs	5,518,331	1,062,446	1,112,741	107,641	1,499,905
Indirect Costs	2,294,836	446,055	436,947	62,098	619,240
Total direct and indirect costs	7,813,167	1,508,501	1,549,689	169,738	2,119,145